

A SURVEY ON PAPR REDUCTION TECHNIQUES FOR MULTIPATH FADING CHANNEL

Vishalakshi Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, PDA College of Engineering, kalaburagi, Karnataka, India vishalakshhii@gmail.com

G. S. Biradar Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, PDA College of Engineering, kalaburagi, Karnataka, India gsbiradar@gmail.com

Vidya Honguntikar Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, Dr. Ambedkar Institute of Technology, Bangalore, Karnataka, India : vidyah91@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The demand for wireless communication is growing gradually from last few years. The increased popularity and usage of wireless multimedia applications has led to the evolution of cellular systems includes 1G, 2G, 3G, 4G and the next generation 5G till date. We can implement novel modulations for orthogonal multiple access (OMA) or use non orthogonal multiple access (NOMA), in order to support higher throughput, massive and heterogeneous connectivity for 5G networks. Traditional Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) possesses high Peak to Average Power Ratio (PAPR) in 5G which degrades the performance of the system. In most of the prior research work different PAPR reduction techniques have been carried out using AWGN (Additive White Gaussian Noise) channel, here we consider the multipath fading channel.

Key Words: OFDM (Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing), OMA (Orthogonal Multiple Access), NOMA (Non Orthogonal Multiple Access), Multipath fading channel, PAPR (Peak to Average Power Ratio).

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, 5G has attracted extensive research and development efforts from the wireless communication system and it is based on 4G technologies, 5G should make an important difference and add more services and benefits to the world over 4G. In order to support large-scale heterogeneous traffic and users, 5G is facing various challenges in wireless multimedia networks, to face new challenges various types of new modulation and multiple access (MA) schemes have been proposed. A 4G system is expected to provide an exhaustive and secure based solution to laptop and mobile devices. The technologies like OFDM, Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) and link adaptation are used in 4G wireless system. Traditional OFDM can no longer satisfy the requirements of 5G, and therefore novel modulation techniques with much lower out of band (OOB) leakage are required. In order to support higher throughput and massive and heterogeneous connectivity for 5G networks, we can adopt novel modulations for OMA or NOMA.

NOMA is one promising technology, which provides high system capacity, low latency, and massive connectivity, to address several challenges in the 5G wireless systems. As the era of the 5G wireless systems approaches, it is difficult for conventional OMA to fulfill the requirements of the super high data rate of user equipment (UE), ultra-low latency, ultra-reliable and massive connectivity. The NOMA technology is becoming a favorable candidate to meet the aforesaid requirements of 5G wireless systems [29]. So far, researchers have made a few overviews and surveys on NOMA techniques, mainly focus on the research of PAPR reduction in NOMA over AWGN channel now here we are going to focus on PAPR reduction in NOMA over multipath fading channel.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years the 5G technology is widely used in mobile communication system, the major drawback of 5G technology is PAPR. To reduce PAPR different technology is used and many of the work considered AWGN channel, here in this we are considering different fading channel. The authors have concentrated on the future network technologies like Denser Multi Radio Access Technologies (RATs) Heterogeneous Network, MIMO System, millimetre Wave Signals, Direct Device to Device

(D2D) communication, Full Duplex (FD) wireless communication to support large-scale heterogeneous traffic and users with high energy efficiency and at low cost to form 5G and device evolution towards 5G [5]. In 5G technology NOMA is considered as a promising candidate in which multiple data flows are superimposed in the power domain and user decoding is based on Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC). Simulation results of this work show that NOMA can ensure high fairness requirements through appropriate PA and is a promising MA scheme for future 5G communication systems [4]. OFDM is an efficient method of data transmission for high speed multimedia communication systems. The main drawback of OFDM system is the high PAPR of the transmitted signals, so to reduce PAPR Coding, phase rotation and clipping, partial transmit sequence (PTS) and selective mapping (SLM) have been proposed to overcome this problem and comparison of performances of the three methods are discussed [3].

After the PTS, SLM, coding, phase rotation, clipping authors introduced Low Density Signature (LDS)-OFDM as an uplink multicarrier multiple access scheme. LDS-OFDM uses LDS structure for spreading the symbols in frequency domain. The performance of LDS-OFDM is evaluated over a typical multipath fading channel under different spectral efficiency conditions and compared with conventional OFDMA systems over multipath fading channel. NOMA has become one of the potential candidates for the upcoming 5G wireless networks due to low latency, higher spectral efficiency, system throughput, and massive connectivity [14]. The uplink NOMA can employ OFDM modulation for the construction of its basic primary signal waveform. The major weakness of uplink NOMA employing OFDM modulation is high PAPR, which makes this scheme inefficient. Therefore, in this Discrete-Sine Transform (DST) matrix precoding based uplink NOMA scheme has been proposed to reduce the higher PAPR. Computer simulations indicate that the DST matrix precoding based uplink NOMA scheme has lower PAPR as compared to the Walsh-Hadamard Transform (WHT) matrix precoding based uplink NOMA scheme and non-precoded uplink NOMA scheme available in the literature [26]

In this authors considered, a novel combination of PAPR reduction and channel estimation techniques for OFDM systems is addressed. OFDM is a spectrally efficient multicarrier modulation technique for high speed data transmission over multipath fading channels [15]. one of the main issues of OFDM is high PAPR of the transmitted signal which adversely affects the complexity of power amplifiers, a number of promising techniques have been proposed and implemented to reduce PAPR of OFDM signal with expense of transmitted signal power, BER, complexity etc. here clipping and filtering, SLM, PTS, linear block coding (LBC), peak insertion (PI) techniques are implemented for PAPR reduction of OFDM signal at transmitter. Comparison of these PAPR reduction techniques is done based on BER performance of the system [23].

Compared to the traditional orthogonal multiple access, NOMA technology can achieve higher spectrum efficiency and support more massive connectivity. Here, authors conducted comprehensive study and comparison on current NOMA technologies that many mainstream companies have proposed for the 5G wireless communication standard. According to the characteristics of the NOMA schemes, we classify these schemes into four categories: scrambling-based NOMA, spreading-based NOMA, coding-based NOMA, and interleaving-based NOMA. By comparing the performance of these technologies, some promising schemes and directions are suggested for the future 5G NOMA developments [27].

In novel broadcasting and communication systems OFDM based NOMA systems are considered as a one of the promising technology. PAPR is the one of the main challenges in OFDM based NOMA system, which degrades the system efficiency. The best PAPR reduction schemes are PTS and precoding and in this precoding method are not good as PTS based ones but PTS-based methods are computationally complex and mostly degrade the system BER. So in this, author concentrated on an efficient PAPR reduction scheme, based on the precoding and dummy sequence insertion (DSI) techniques, to overcome the previous limitations. Furthermore, a novel dummy sequence generation procedure is devised for the proposed method. The developed scheme has a remarkably better PAPR reduction and BER performance than the precoding and PTS-based approaches. Moreover, it is

computationally much less complex compared to the PTS methods [30]. Due to low latency, higher spectral efficiency, system throughput, and massive connectivity NOMA is considered as a one of the potential candidate for upcoming 5G wireless networks. PAPR is considered as a major weakness of uplink NOMA employing OFDM modulation, which makes this scheme inefficient. Therefore, in this author proposed the Discrete-Sine Transform (DST) matrix precoding based uplink NOMA scheme to reduce the higher PAPR. Computer simulations indicate that the DST matrix precoding based uplink NOMA scheme has lower PAPR as compared to the Walsh-Hadamard Transform (WHT) matrix precoding based uplink NOMA scheme and non-precoded uplink NOMA scheme available in the literature [31].

NOMA is one of the potential candidates for future radio access to address the increasing demands of mobile traffic. NOMA-based systems employ OFDM for multicarrier modulation which induces PAPR. High PAPR makes conventional NOMA systems spectrally and energy inefficient. Thus, in this author proposed precoded NOMA system to overcome the PAPR problem in downlink NOMA. Different unitary transforms such as Walsh Hadamard transform (WHT), Zadoff chu transform (ZCT), and discrete Hartley transform (DCT) are applied as linear precoding techniques to overcome the PAPR problem in NOMA. Moreover, a new precoding technique TT-transform is also proposed which is a hybrid combination of WHT and ZCT. Link-level performance of power domain NOMA is analysed in terms of PAPR, spectral efficiency, bit error rate, and computational complexity. Simulation results show that in the presence of linear precoding techniques, performance of classic NOMA systems improve at the cost of slight increment in complexity [32]. The idea of research is to propose an OMA technique called NOMA, which is different from conventional orthogonal access methods. It is essential to calculate the BER of the users at the receiver by considering the wireless channel characteristics with different fading effects [29].

3. PAPR Reduction Techniques

In the literature review, many PAPR reduction techniques have been suggested to control the PAPR problem; a large PAPR would push the HPAs into saturation, making interference among the subcarriers at the transmitter which degrades the performance of BER. The PAPR reduction technique through AWGN channel is studied here we are concentrating on reduction of PAPR using multipath fading channel. Multiple Access is achieved in OFDMA by assigning subsets of subcarriers to individual users. OFDM is a multi carrier modulation technique which divides the available spectrum into many carriers. OFDM provides high spectral efficiency, low implementation complexity, less vulnerability to echoes and non linear distortion. Due to these advantages of the OFDM system, it is vastly used in various communication systems. One of the major disadvantages of OFDM is its large PAPR of transmitting signals and reduces the efficiency of the power amplifier. OFDM signals have a large PAPR due to the superposition of all subcarrier signals with varying amplitude.

One of the major disadvantages of OFDM is its large PAPR of transmitting signals, which increases the complexity of the Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) in the transmitter and reduces the efficiency of the power amplifier. Large PAPR occurred at the power amplifier causes the amplifier to switch from linear region of operation to non-linear region. These nonlinearities can result in significant spectral spreading and in-band distortion which degrades the system performance. Therefore, for zero distortion of the OFDM signals, the high power amplifier (HPA) must not only operate in its linear region but also with sufficient back-off. Thus, HPA with a large dynamic range is required for OFDM systems. These amplifiers are very expensive and are vital components of the OFDM system. Thus, if we reduce the PAPR; it not only means that we are reducing the cost of OFDM system and reducing the complexity of ADC and DAC, but also increasing the transmit power.

To reduce the PAPR value of OFDM system, there are several techniques have been proposed. In clipping and filtering PAPR reduction technique, any subcarrier having amplitude more than threshold value is clipped or that subcarrier is filtered to bring out a lower PAPR value. There is BER

performance degradation in this method. In Coding PAPR reduction scheme, Complement Block Coding (CBC) uses complementary bits to reduce occurrence probability of peak signals by expansion of bandwidth. Partial Transmission Sequence (PTS) PAPR reduction technique, involves transmitting only part of data of varying subcarrier that covers all the information to be sent in the signal which requires side information needed to send to receiver. In Selective Mapping (SLM) PAPR reduction technique, a set of sufficiently different data blocks representing the information same as the original data blocks are selected. Selection of data blocks with low PAPR value makes it suitable for transmission but has complexity in implementation. These techniques achieve PAPR reduction at the expense of transmitter signal power increase, BER increase, data rate loss, computational complexity increase, and so on.

Precoding based PAPR reduction technique is a simple linear technique that does not require any side information for implementation. This scheme does not require any power increase, side information and complex optimizations and also does not lose the data rate and spectral efficiency. Some of the most promising techniques are NOMA is to utilize power and/or code domains in multiplexing to support more users in the same resource block. There are three major types of NOMA: power-domain NOMA, code-domain NOMA and NOMA multiplexing in multiple domains. Comparing to power domain NOMA and NOMA multiplexing in multiple domains Code domain NOMA considered as more advantageous

To reduce the PAPR value of OFDM system and NOMA, there are several techniques have been proposed.

1. Amplitude clipping and filtering

Clipping is a straightforward and simple effective technique for PAPR reduction which limits the maximum of transmit signal to a pre-specified threshold value. It will clip the peak amplitude of amplification. The clipping is followed by filtering to reduce out of band power. Clipping method is a nonlinear process and may cause in or out distortion into the OFDM system, which imposes out of band interference signals to adjacent channels and may affect the BER performance. Out-of-band interference can be reduced by filtering but it cannot reduce in-band distortion.

2. Selective mapping

In this a set of sufficiently different data blocks representing the information same as the original data blocks are selected. The input data sequences are multiplied by each of the phase sequences to generate alternative input symbol sequences and apply IFFT operation, and then one which has a lowest PAPR is selected for transmission. Implementation of this technique is complex. Some extension of SLM is also proposed to reduce the complexity and number of the bits for side information transmission [30].

3. Partial transmit sequence

PTS is another very effective approach and one of the most important methods that is used to reduce PAPR in the OFDM system and it can be presented in two main steps. First, by dividing the original OFDM signal into a number of sub blocks. Secondly, adding the phase rotated sub-blocks to develop a number of candidate signals to pick the one with smallest PAPR for transmission

4. Coding

The coding is used for two purposes, error correction and PAPR reduction. This reduces the hardware complexity of the system but there is bandwidth expansion.

5. Precoding

The precoding based techniques are simple linear techniques and hence easy to implement without the need of any side information. This scheme does not require any power increase, side information and complex optimizations and also does not lose the data rate and spectral efficiency [26].

6. Discrete Cosine Transform

The PAPR can be reduced by using transformation is to reduce the autocorrelation of the input sequence before the IFFT operation is applied. A close relation exist between the PAPR of an OFDM signal and the aperiodic autocorrelation function (ACF) of an input signal [26, 31].

7. Hadamard Transform.

Hadamard matrices are simple in structures, they are square, and have elements + 1 or -1. It will reduce the occurrence of the high peaks comparing the original OFDM system. Hadamard matrix have mutually orthogonal row vectors and orthogonal column vectors, means every two different rows in this matrix represent two perpendicular vectors. The idea to use the orthogonal rows of or columns to reduce the autocorrelation of the input sequence and it requires no side information to be transmitted to the receiver.

It is well-known that the original OFDM signals have a very sharp power spectrum. This is affected by the PAPR reduction schemes that are slower spectrum roll-off, more spectrum side-lobes, and higher adjacent channel interference. Clipping technique causes spectrum side-lobes. DCT on the other hand, will reduce side-lobes and out-of-band distortion in SLM shows a better PAPR performances but it has spectrum regrowth. Compared to SLM, PTS has similar PSD as original OFDM [29].

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we have reviewed the research contributions of NOMA to reduce PAPR over AWGN channel for 5G wireless Networks. 5G is far more superior to its previous generations when it comes to characteristics. NOMA with new technologies can deliver lower latency, higher throughput and ultra reliability, so it has been widely recognized as a promising way to scale up the number of users, enhance the spectral efficiency, and improve the user fairness in wireless networks. NOMA is one of the fundamental multiple access technology in spectral efficiency, and the benefits over its closest contemporary multiple access scheme OFDMA are significantly better, PAPR reduction technique will be developed for low data rate loss and efficient use of channel. In this work, a PAPR reduction techniques for NOMA over multipath fading channel was proposed, where previous work considered only AWGN channel. This technique will improve the spectral efficiency and the BER performance of the system.

REFERENCE

- [1]. Yinlin Xu; Jianfeng Weng “*Group-Orthogonal OFDMA in Fast Time-Varying Frequency-Selective Fading Environments*,” 60th Vehicular Technology Conference, 2004. VTC 2004- fall. IEEE 2004.
- [2]. Tariq Jamil; Saifullah Khanzada; Ali Ramadan Ali “*An Analytical Model For SLTDM to Reduce the PAPR and ICI in OFDM Systems for Fast Varying Channels*,” International Multitopic Conference, IEEE 2006.
- [3]. K.Ram Mohan Rao, T.Sravanti “*Performance Analysis of OFDM System Using PAPR Reduction Technique*” International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER) Vol.3, Issue.2, March-April. 2013 pp-715-720.
- [4]. Shilpa Talwar, Debabani Choudhury, Konstantinos Dimou, Ehsan Aryafar, Boyd Bangerter, Kenneth Stewart “*Enabling Technologies and Architectures for 5G Wireless*”, by Intel Corporation, Santa Clara, CA IEEE 2014.
- [5]. Yejian Chen, Frank Schaich, and Thorsten Wild “*Multiple Access and Waveforms for 5G: IDMA and Universal Filtered Multi-Carrier*”, by Bell Laboratories, Alcatel-Lucent, IEEE 2014.
- [6]. Stelios Timotheou, Member, IEEE, and Ioannis Krikidis, Senior Member, IEEE, “*Fairness for Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access in 5G Systems*”, April 2015.
- [7]. Tao Yunzheng, Liu Long, Liu Shang, and Zhang Zhi “*A Survey: Several Technologies of Non-Orthogonal Transmission for 5G*” China Communications October 2015.
- [8]. Panagiotis D. Diamantoulakis, Koralia N. Pappi, Zhiguo Ding, and George K. Karagiannidis Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, “*Optimal Design of Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access with Wireless Power Transfer*”, IEEE Wireless Commun. Lett. vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 265–268, Jun. 2015.
- [9]. Shanzhi Chen, Senior Member, IEEE, Bin Ren, Qiubin Gao, Shaoli Kang, Shaohui Sun, and Kai Niu “*Pattern Division Multiple Access (PDMA) -A Novel Non-orthogonal Multiple Access for 5G Radio Networks*”, IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology 2016.
- [10]. Zahra Sharifian, Mohammad Javad Omidi, Hamid Saeedi-Sourck, and Arman Farhan “*Linear Precoding for PAPR Reduction of GFDM*”, IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, Vol. 5, No. 5, October 2016.
- [11]. Brahim Akbil, Driss Aboutajdine, “*Improved IDMA for Multiple Access of 5G*”, International Journal of Communication Networks and Information Security (IJCNIS) Vol. 7, No. 3, December 2015.
- [12]. Gilberto Berardinelli, Frank Frederiksen, Klaus Pedersen, Preben Mogensen, Kari Pajukoski “*Reference Sequence design for Zero-Tail DFT-spread- OFDM*”, Department of Electronic Systems, Aalborg University, Denmark, IEEE Wireless Conference and Networking Conference (WCNC 2016).

- [13]. Krzysztof Wesolowski, Adrian Langowski, and Krzysztof "A Novel Pilot Scheme for 5G Downlink Transmission", Bakowski Chair of Wireless Communications Poznan University of Technology Poznan, Poland, IEEE 2015.
- [14]. Reza Hoshyar, Razieh Razavi and Mohammed AL-Imari "LDS-OFDM an Efficient Multiple Access Technique", Centre for Communication Systems Research University of Surrey Guildford GU2 7XH, Surrey, U.K, IEEE 2010.
- [15]. Anh Tai Ho, Jean-François Helard, Youssef Nasser "A novel combined PAPR reduction and channel estimation approach for OFDM systems" International Symposium on Broadband Multimedia Systems and Broadcasting(BMSB) IEEE 2010.
- [16]. Shunqing Zhang, Xiuqiang Xu, Yiqun Wu and Lei Lu Huawei Technologies, "5G: Towards Energy-Efficient, Low-Latency and High-Reliable Communications Networks", Proceedings of the IEEE ICCS 2014.
- [17]. Pekka Pirinen centre for wireless communications Finland,"A Brief Overview of 5G Activities", 1st International conference on 5G for Ubiquitous Connectivity 2014.
- [18]. Renato L.G. Cavalcante, Slawomir Stan'czak, Martin Schubert, Andreas Eisenblätter, and Ulrich Türke, "Toward Energy-Efficient 5G Wireless Communications Technologies", IEEE Signal Processing Magazine, November 2014.
- [19]. Alessio Zappone, Luca Sanguinetti, Giacomo Bacci, Eduard Jorswieck, "Energy-Efficient Power Control: A Look at 5G Wireless Technologies",IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC15), London, UK,June 8 – 12, 2014.
- [20]. Shilpa Talwar, Debabani Choudhury, Konstantinos Dimou, Ehsan Aryafar, Boyd Bangerter, Kenneth Stewart Intel Corporation, Santa Clara, CA, "Enabling Technologies and Architectures for 5G Wireless",IEEE trans. 2014.
- [21]. Zhiguo Ding, Yuanwei Liu, Jinho Choi, Qi Sun, Maged ElKashlan, Chih-Lin I and H. Vincent Poor, "Application of Non-orthogonal Multiple Access in LTE and 5G Networks", a manuscript submitted to the IEEE communications magazine November 2015.
- [22]. Pongsatorn Sedtheetorn, Tatcha Chulajata, "Accurate Spectral Efficiency Analysis for Non Orthogonal Multiple Access", ICACT Transactions on Advanced Communications Technology (TACT) Vol. 5, Issue 3, May 2016.
- [23]. P. Preenu Ann; Renu Jose "Comparison of PAPR reduction techniques in OFDM systems" International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES) 2016.
- [24]. Zedong Xie; Xihong Chen; Yongjin Liu "A channel estimation algorithm for MIMO-SCFDE systems over fast time-varying multipath channels," IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing (ICSPCC) 2017.
- [25]. Mouna BEN MABROUK, Marwa CHAFII, Yves LOUËT and Faouzi BADER "A Precoding-based PAPR Reduction Technique for UF-OFDM and Filtered-OFDM Modulations in 5G Systems" IETR/CentraleSupélec, Campus de Rennes, 35511 Cesson-Sevigné, France, European Wireless 2017.
- [26]. Imran Baig, Najam ul Hasan, Manaf Zghaibeh, Imran Ullah Khan and Abdul Sattar Saand "A DST Precoding Based Uplink NOMA Scheme for PAPR Reduction in 5G Wireless Network", Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, IEEE 2017.
- [27]. Zhanji Wu Kun Lu; Chengxin Jiang ; Xuanbo Shao "Comprehensive Study and Comparison on 5G NOMA Schemes" IEEE Access (Volume: 6) March 2018.
- [28]. JIE ZENG ,REN PING LIU, MINGYAO PENG , CHANG WANG , And JIAJIA Mei" Investigation on Evolving Single-Carrier NOMA into Multi-Carrier NOMA in 5G" Digital Object Identifier 0.1109/ACCESS.2018.2868093.
- [29]. A.Vasuki and P.Vijayakumar "Analysis of Error Rate for NOMA System over Different Fading Channel" Department of ECE, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai, India 2020.
- [30]. Rezasayyari Jafarpourrostam Hamedahmadi "Efficient PAPR Reduction Scheme for OFDM-NOMA Systems Based On DSI & Precoding Methods "https://doi.org/10.1016/J.Phycom.2021.101372.
- [31]. Arsla Khan , Soo Young Shin "Linear Precoding Techniques for OFDM- Based NOMA over Frequency-Selective Fading Channels" IETE Journal Research volume 63 30 Mar 20